

Sighting of Eurasian Wryneck *Jynx torquilla* (Linnaeus, 1758) from Belagavi: North Karnataka, Southern India

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Eurasian Wryneck *Jynx torquilla* is a peculiar, medium sized cryptic grey, buff and brown colored bird with nightjar plumage resembles woodpeckers. It is a winter visitor mainly winters in Eastern Pakistan to Himachal Pradesh, Assam and in south India up to northern part of Maharashtra and Andhra Pradesh. Eurasian Wryneck also winters in Nepal, Bhutan and Bangladesh. It breeds during May-July in Northwest Himalayas, from East Pakistan to Himachal Pradesh at 1500-3300 m (Grimmett *et al.*, 1998 & 2011; Kazmierczak, 2000; Ali S., 2002; Rasmussen & Anderton, 2012). It is a least concerned bird having larger distribution range from Africa, Europe and in Asian subcontinent (IUCN, 2015; Birdlife, 2015). In India it is distributed almost throughout the Indian union. It inhabits the orchards, cultivation edges, semi desert, mixed deciduous and open scrub forest area. In this note we report new sighting record of Eurasian Wryneck from Belagavi, north Karnataka in southern India.

On 09.12.2014 we are on the way birding trip to Western Ghats towards Goa. We surprisingly spotted an unidentified bird at 08.48 AM nearby Kusamalli village along the State Highway 54 in Khanapur taluk of Belagavi district in north Karnataka. Bird was there on

the tree branches for 2-3 minutes and flew in to the nearby forest. Bird was photographed by Nikon D5100 and identified as Eurasian Wryneck (Figure 1) using field guide by Grimmett *et al.*, (2011) on the field itself. Figure 2 shows exact sighting location of Eurasian Wryneck.

The distribution map by Grimmett *et al.* (1998) shows few isolated records of Eurasian Wryneck in southern India. But the distribution maps by Grimmett *et al.* (2011) and Kazmierczak (2000) not showing recent sighting records of the said bird in southern India. Whereas, distribution map given by Rasmussen & Anderton (2012) and Arlott (2014) not showing its range in Southern India. Therefore present sighting record of Eurasian Wryneck in southern India is worth of its documentation. Since, there is no published literature of Eurasian Wryneck sighting from Belagavi. It becomes the first photographic sighting record from Belagavi.

Figure-1. Shows Eurasian Wryneck *Jynx torquilla* sighted in Belagavi, North Karnataka

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Conflict of Interests

Authors declare that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this paper.

Figure-2. Shows sighting location of Eurasian Wryneck *Jynx torquilla* in Belagavi, North Karnataka

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